

Recommended citation: Bernard, J., Edström, K., De Laet, T., & Van den Bogaard, M. (2020). Lessons Learned in the Doctoral Symposium in Engineering Education Research at SEFI 2020. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1464-1476). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14654527](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654527).

LESSONS LEARNED IN THE DOCTORAL SYMPOSIUM IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION RESEARCH AT SEFI 2020

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Keywords: Engineering Education Research, doctoral education, networking

ABSTRACT

The 4th Doctoral Symposium at SEFI 2020 attracted 21 doctoral students and 17 senior researchers. For the first time, it was organised as a fully online event. In preparation, the doctoral students wrote extended abstracts to introduce themselves and their PhD projects, while the seniors provided reading tips and advice. The intense, full-day program was based on group discussions and interactive plenary sessions. The Doctoral Symposium was concluded by a session in which each participant presented their take-home message. This paper outlines how the Doctoral Symposium was organised and summarizes some of the documentation.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The SEFI Doctoral Symposium

With the exception of a few larger research centres, doctoral education in engineering education research (EER) is often organised in relatively small scale at each institution – this is not least true in Europe. Therefore, it is important for PhD students to network outside their own research environment, in order to enhance the doctoral student experience, support their development as researchers, and increase their understanding of the EER field as a whole. Networks, both regional and international, can also be seen as an act of creating and maintaining connections to strengthen the research field as a whole [1, 2].

The European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI) recognises the EER field and its importance for furthering engineering education. Through the Doctoral Symposium in Engineering Education Research, SEFI offers PhD students opportunities to share their work with peers and with senior researchers, to build their network, and exchange feedback. The purpose is that participants will:

- meet other students and supervisors to extend their network and view of the EER field,
- present and discuss their own work and the work of others,
- get perspectives from scholars outside their own institution,
- contribute to the conference and the SEFI EER community, and
- promote collaborative research and elaborate future research directions.

In three previous SEFI conferences, a Doctoral Symposium in Engineering Education Research (DS) has been held as full-day pre-conference events: before the SEFI Annual Conference 2016 in Tampere, 2018 in Copenhagen, and 2019 in Budapest. The purpose of this paper is to document and share some insights into the process and products from the DS 2020. In the following, we discuss recruitment of participants – both the doctoral students and experienced researchers, and explain the activity design. We present parts of the rich material that was created, in particular the advice from seniors and the individual reflections from all participants.

1.2 The First Online Symposium

This year, due to the Covid pandemic, the DS had to be arranged online, just like the SEFI2020 conference. Travel restrictions had been in place during the six months preceding the DS, and many had been working mainly from home. It had already become obvious that the lack of mobility and networking was a tough consequence for doctoral education. The scarcity of opportunities to build their own networks can be expected to be particularly serious for those who do not already have established connections that they can draw on. Therefore, the DS had a more important function this year than ever before.

The challenge when organising the event online is that, due to the nature of the event, the personal meeting is in focus. Therefore, it was particularly important not to lose the human, friendly, informal atmosphere. On the positive side, however, the

pandemic had also forced a quick uptake of online meeting formats, and the organisers never hesitated to redesign the event for fully remote participation.

1.3 Doctoral Student Participants

The doctoral students interested in participating were invited to send an extended abstract containing a *general introduction* (background and interest in EER), an *outline of their research* (elevator pitch, research interest, thesis title, supervisors, current work), *reflections* (questions, challenges, dilemmas, wishes and ambitions) and *preferences for networking* (at SEFI2020, and keeping in touch). The extended abstracts that were submitted showed that the doctoral students were in various stages in their PhD projects, representing a variety in topics from policy level to fine-grained class room studies. The 21 doctoral students that were accepted came from 10 countries: Australia, Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Hungary, New Zealand, the Netherlands, South Africa, Sweden, and the UK.

1.4 Senior Participants

A number of experienced researchers in the field – here called senior participants – were invited to provide the PhD students with feedback, coaching and guidance. It is important for the DS to have a high number of seniors. Just like in the previous symposia, the organisers wanted to keep the ratio of seniors to students very high, aiming at approximately 2 seniors per 3 doctoral students. The invitations were apparently very attractive, as almost every person agreed to volunteer their time. This year there were in total 17 seniors, including the organising team (the authors of this paper). They came from Argentina, Australia, Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, Switzerland, the UK, and the US. Hence, the seniors were even slightly more geographically diverse as the doctoral students.

1.5 Groups

The core of the symposium was the group activities in which doctoral students and seniors worked together. Six groups were formed, each containing 3-4 doctoral students. The groups were composed taking into account a balance between diversity and similarity regarding years of experience, research interests – both topics and methods, university and country. To address the problems of participating from different time zones, some seniors were paired so that, at lunchtime, the two seniors from Australia were succeeded by US-based seniors. To guarantee continuity, each group had at least one European senior who participated the full day. Hence, groups contained 2 or 3 seniors. The groups were formed a week in advance, and a compilation of all extended abstracts were sent out. The instruction was to prepare by reading the abstracts of the doctoral students, at least the ones in their own group.

1.6 Event Outline

The event took place on Sunday September 20, as a pre-conference day before the SEFI 2020 Annual Conference. The program was designed to accommodate lively and deep discussions between PhD students and experienced researchers. The main parts of the program were group activities, interspersed with plenary activities:

09.00 – 09.10	Arriving in Zoom
09.10 – 09.20	Introduction & how the DS will work
09.20 – 10.00	2-minute introductions of seniors Break
10.15 – 12.15	First group session Lunch
13.00 – 13.45	Speed dating, 6 x 6 minutes
13.45 – 14.45	Second group session Break
15.00 – 16.00	Plenary report: Take-home messages

2 DOCUMENTED RESULTS

2.1 Reading Tips from Experienced Researchers

The senior participants were asked to submit some reading tips in advance, prompted by these questions:

- If a doctoral student wanted to read something by you, what would you recommend and why?
- Recommend one paper (not your own) for a starting PhD student?

These prompts resulted in a comprehensive collection of publications:

Lisa Benson chose a paper examining how students think about what it means to do engineering and be an engineer [3], pushing back on some narrow ways of thinking that are passed on from generation to generation of engineering students. She also recommended a “*readable paper that explains knowledge transfer, an important and complex concept in education*” [4].

Jonte Bernhard offered a paper on learning in laboratories [5] which demonstrates how engineering education can be improved through design-based research, as well as a book chapter in which he compares engineering education research with engineering research [6]. Together with Caroline Baillie he has also written about quality in EER [7]. Finally, he recommended an editorial by Jennifer Case that demonstrates the importance of being critical and going beyond *fads and jargon* [8].

Maartje van den Bogaard mentioned her paper on student retention [9], which “*introduces complexity theory into thinking about educational issues. It also shows the synergy from collaborating with researchers from different fields and contexts, who are driven to understand a shared problem*”. She also promoted a paper by Padilla as “*a game-changer in thinking about student success and with an exemplary research design for a qualitative study*” [10].

Shannon Chance recommended a paper discussing methods, and with findings of interviews with teachers who implemented PBL showing how they overcame challenges and maintained enthusiasm for a difficult change [11]. She also pointed to the classic paper by Case and Light [12], as it “*captures what was happening in EER at a specific point in time and reflects the socially constructed nature of our field*”. The same paper was also recommended by both Anne Gardner and Roger Hadgraft.

Kristina Edström invited the doctoral students to take a historical excursion [13], and reflect on the EER field [1, 14]. She also recommended them to subscribe to updates of the latest articles in the European Journal of Engineering Education [15-19]. Some of these were published just days before the DS [15, 16].

Cindy Finelli offered “a quick introduction to my research on student resistance to active learning, and practical implications for educators” [20]. Her other suggestion was a paper by Borrego, discussing difficulties for engineers learning educational research methods [21].

Anne Gardner picked a paper in the general higher education literature [22], rather than an engineering education specific publication.

Roger Hadgraft recommended a recent overview of future educational models together with Kolmos [23].

Anette Kolmos introduced a new publication with a longitudinal perspective on PBL [24] and mentioned her literature review with Chen [17].

Tinne De Laet chose a paper that “reflects the kind of work I love to do – research that impacts actual education, staff, and students. We show the dashboards we have deployed at our university to support first-year students, and the research connected to it” [25]. The topic of her other recommendation was self-regulated learning [26].

Greet Langie chose a recent systematic literature review on early career engineers [27], and a review related to achievement [28].

Rui Lima recommended a paper on PBL with a deep interaction of students and companies [29]. His other choice addresses conceptualization and reflection about active learning [30].

Wim Van Petegem picked an international cross-disciplinary study on how to network as PhD students while learning in the digital world [31]. His other choice was a book, *The Digital Scholar* [32].

Maria Isabel Pozzo recommended a paper about a very useful data collection technique in empirical research, namely the survey [33], and she also recommended the first chapters in the book *Formation of a Scientific Mind* [34].

Johannes Strobel chose a paper highlighting that “problem solving is a lot more complex and nuanced than often taught in engineering” [26]; Tinne De Laet also recommended this paper. His next choice investigates how empathy is conceptualized in the engineering context [35]. Finally, he picked an investigation of students' motivation to study engineering [36], as “it is so rare we do longitudinal studies. This is a very good example of what such a study can contribute”.

Roland Tormey pointed to a paper on the impact of gender on group work [37], featuring data in naturalistic settings and co-authored with a group of master students. His other choice is a useful paper on systematic reviews [38].

Esther Ventura-Medina offered a paper related to group work, on student teams' strategies in their first PBL experience [39]. Her other suggestion is an influential paper on research methods [40].

2.2 Advice from Experienced Researchers

In their advance input, seniors were also asked to give one general tip for a starting PhD student. Below, the tips are in random order and somewhat edited for space:

Lisa Benson: Figure out what direction you want to go with in your research and narrow this down to a research question, or questions. First: What are you passionate about - what

made you pursue a PhD in engineering education? Second: What are some of the greatest needs in our world right now – what needs your attention? The intersection of these two ideas is your sweet spot – this is the area that deserves your attention and that will carry you through all the trials and tribulations of completing a PhD.

Jonte Bernhard: Visit other research groups for shorter (or longer) periods. Even if your supervisor and research group are the Best in the World you always learn something by contact with other researchers. It broadens your views.

Maartje van den Bogaard: Writing is a form of processing information, of sharpening your understanding, of creating a source to work with when you are ready to write your dissertation. Start writings right away. It is between a craft and an art. It is something you can learn. Your writing doesn't have to be pretty, it needs to do the job of communicating your ideas. Start bare bones with short sentences. The rest will follow.

Shannon Chance: Find optimistic and supportive supervisors and mentors.

Kristina Edström: Read, read, read... Explore themes, people, journals. Follow references and read even more. Note what is convincing. Note what makes effective writing.

Cynthia Finelli: Be kind to yourself - tending to your own physical and mental well-being is at least as important as making progress in your research!

Anne Gardner: Apply project management skills to your PhD.

Roger Hadgraft: The clearer you can state your problem, the easier it is to answer. Limit your scope to a problem that can be investigated within the time available. Also make sure that the data you need can be collected without unreasonable difficulty.

Annette Kolmos: Work on your research question.

Tinne De Laet: Build a relationship of mutual understanding, trust, and openness with your supervisor. Be open about your aims, doubts, and things that make you happy.

Greet Langie: Take your time to read, to decide what interests you most and to design your research methodology.

Rui Lima: Find a research topic that really motivates you.

Wim Van Petegem: Three things are important: 1. Focus, 2. Focus, and 3. Focus!

Maria Isabel Pozzo: Set fixed time in your weekly agenda to devote to work on your thesis. If you wait to have free time to work on it, it will never come; it's up to you to make it.

Johannes Strobel: Keep track and explore what puzzles you – these puzzlements are great building blocks for research questions and research careers. Read what others have written in the area of your puzzlement.

Roland Tormey: Develop the skill of writing for a diverse audience at the beginning. This makes your life (probably also the relationship with your supervisor) much easier.

Esther Ventura-Medina: Take ownership of your research work – take initiative and be involved :-)

2.3 Group Notes

The six groups wrote collaborative notes during their time together, in total 3 hours. A Google Document was prepared with space for each group. The downloaded version of the notes is 15 pages long in total, and it is outside the scope of this report to analyse this comprehensive material. However, the groups seem to have followed the suggestions in the instructions, as the notes contain generous amounts of:

- Interesting things that resonate with us
- Ideas and strengths that we have identified
- Problems, questions or issues we have identified
- Tips, things to do, read or think about

2.4 Take-home Messages

Each participant was asked to formulate a short nugget of wisdom as a take-home message from the DS. In the final plenary session, each participant had 1 minute to present their take-home message. The recommended length was 1-2 sentences or maximum 100 words; below some of the messages have been edited for space.

Lisa Benson: We are all feeling a bit disconnected, even those of us who are not lone wolves, so it is important to be intentional about connecting with others. Reach out to other grad students or recent graduates to discuss each others' research, read and review each others' papers and provide each other with resources. Create your own research group online, which isn't so strange at the moment since we are all working online.

Ljubov van Beek: Whatever you are going through - you are not alone. PhD is a self-development project.

Jonte Bernhard: I am glad that so many could participate today. It was the largest number of doctoral students since the start of the Doctoral Symposium. I hope the meeting inspired you and you have learned something. You can always learn something by extending your network and you get new perspectives from visiting other institutes, and communicating with people outside your own close circle. Never stop to keep your mind open!

Anders Melbye Boelt: Create and support the development of networks with other PhD students researching a similar topic.

Maartje van den Bogaard: Serendipity is key in all we do: without serendipity, none of us would be working in this field. I think we need to cherish the idea that research in and pathways towards EER are not linear and depend on things out of our control.

Anita Campbell: It is possible to form connections with new people online. It's so useful to get a glimpse of how others work and think.

Shannon Chance: Journal manuscripts that get rejected at first and then later published get higher citations than those accepted by the first journal [Ball, P. (2012). Rejection improves eventual impact of manuscripts. *Nature*.]

Kurt Coppens: Pay attention to understanding the context of papers (e.g. cultural difference), especially when dealing with feedback literature. Writing for yourself is a good way to crystallize information. Find a coding system when reading papers and after a while try to summarize the codes.

Tinne De Laet: Whatever you do, make sure you know why, and keep on believing in what you do. You are not alone!

Kristina Edström: John Ruskin wrote "*the highest reward for man's toil is not what he gets for it, but what he becomes by it*". Therefore, think less about "getting" a PhD, and more about who you want to become by doing it. What skills do you want to develop, what do you want to learn about, what kind of work do you want to prepare yourself for, what kind of expert do you want to be seen as? There are so many things you can shape in your PhD project to accommodate the learning that you desire.

Sina Enteshari: Getting to listen to other students struggles and hearing supervisor advice on how the research should be was superb. The discussion in our group was always evolving, and we covered different concepts. As an engineer, I found it interesting that for success in social science, you have to be a Friendly Cultural Stranger and keep asking questions from everyone in the faculty.

Cynthia Finelli: Be kind to yourself - tending to your own physical and mental well being is at least as important as making progress in your research! When planning where to publish your results, find the right journal. It isn't always about impact factor. Who is your intended audience? What you want them to take away from your writing? There are many related journals where you could publish, find one that FITS your goals.

Anne Gardner: Wherever we are on the researcher development trajectory, there are challenges dealing with what can look like interesting opportunities – it is always a good idea to think at least a little before saying yes – does this exciting looking opportunity align with my overall values/purpose?

Marta Gavioli: Educational Design Based Research goes from theory to practice to theory again, we are quite free in the methods to use as long as we can defend them

Roger Hadgraft: Focus! Get very clear about what issue you are trying to investigate. This will almost certainly mean you need to narrow your focus as time goes on because most studies start too broad at the beginning. This will require constant refinement of your research question.

Jolan Hanssens: Roger Hadgraft said: *“Education is not a stationary process. There is never a final answer. A group of people today will think differently than a group of people 10 years from now. Education is in that sense much more complex than, say, physics.”* This highlights the value of different viewpoints. This is trivial to acknowledge but harder to really understand. The prevailing paradigm today might become irrelevant tomorrow after all. It is important to always keep an open mind.

Melanie Herzig: One of the most important things is to be sure about what you really want to measure in your study. Only then you can find the exact wording for your research question.

Ferdinand Kieckhäfer: Always state and motivate the choices I make (sometimes subconsciously) while researching.

Anette Kolmos: Always great to hear about the PhD students research projects. The process is very similar and the problems the same.

Nárcisz Kulcsár: The biggest problem in mathematics education is that the connections between mathematics and real life are not taught clearly. Knowing that something is useful enhances inner motivation.

Greet Langie: Each PhD student has different hurdles. Maybe you don't enjoy it for the moment, but at the end of your journey you will discover that the hurdles helped you discover new horizons. Enjoy the hurdles! Do not be afraid of walking new methodological ground, as long as you can defend it and provide justification for your work, all things were once new.

Mariana Leandro Cruz: As PhD students, we should be in contact with researchers (different from our supervisors) who see our projects in different perspectives. This gives us new insights that can complement our researcher.

Rui Lima: In the beginning, read and talk as most as you can about engineering education and EER topics that you will be struggling with. Don't be afraid of failing during the research

process, but learn with it. Once I heard in an ironic way that we do not finish a PhD, we quit it. And this idea was helpful for some of my PhD researchers to close and finish their work.

Ellen Lynch: We all struggle - but it is by struggling that we learn something.

Daphne Miedema: Work with researchers in different disciplines to find new perspectives.

Xin Ming: PhD research is about careful work in a well-defined area; To research is to find connection points among methods, theories, questions, observations and so on; To report about methodology is to convince others why your method is the right one for your question and give enough description about how it is applied; Having contacts with real people, both peers and seniors, is precious, especially in such a time when we meet through screens.

Ashlee Pearson: Imposter syndrome can creep in and make you doubt yourself and the validity of your research and results. Have faith in the processes outlined by the literature and those who have walked before you. If you're following a known and trusted process, you're going to be going ok, it's just the self doubt creeping in.

Wim van Petegem: Three things are important for a PhD researcher: 1. Focus (on the topic), 2. Focus (on the process), 3. Focus (on the life beyond). To become a good author, become a good reviewer. Build your own network – it is a transversal competence.

Maria Isabel Pozzo: Even in a forced online edition of the symposium there is a variety of activities that can be carried out to exchange and to learn from each other.

Iresha Ranaraja: PhD is a journey with lots of ups and downs and added to that we have so much uncertainty around. Connecting with peers and getting constructive feedback from seniors from a supportive community like this gets you inspired and motivated to do better.

Elieen Sijmkens: Make your research question very clear and specific, but also to identify the different elements of the question and decide in which elements you want to dig deeper.

Indunil Sikurajapathi: Explore more literature around your research topic. Find out if your research question has been answered before. You might need to refine or narrow down your research question. If you also teach, have a clear schedule for your research, and plan considerable time for your research. Learn how not to say 'YES' to everything. Learn when to say 'No'. Be Assertive! Feeling 'overwhelmed' is not a negative sign. It means your mind is caring about what you are doing!

Kristian Skytt Nilsson: Focus on the goal and sort the data. Smooth sea never made a skilled sailor.

Johannes Strobel: Howard Thurman: *"Don't ask what the world needs. Ask yourself what makes you come alive, and then go do it. Because what the world needs is people who have come alive."* I get reminded that this is a field and research area where different fields meet. My standpoint(s) of origin are important. Coming from education and going to engineering is different than the other way around... Life experience, phenomena, beliefs I bring, worldviews... all impact. Being aware of where I stand is important to expand.

Roland Tormey: Writing for diverse audiences is important in Engineering Education Research. Some readers are engineers, others are educationalists. Some do quantitative research, some do qualitative. Some do experimental research, some do cross-sectional research, and some do design-based research. They have different prior knowledge and different assumptions. You need to write in a way which communicates to all of them... Writing is a skill that needs to be developed (...and you never stop learning from feedback by reviewers, readers, etc.).

Esther Ventura-Medina: Wonderful to see so many young enthusiastic people. Taking ownership of the research is very important – being passionate and interested about your research work is key to success. It is similarly important to have a clear research question which can help you to define a methodology and data collection methods that can answer that question. Finally, some days are more difficult than others – research is always challenging in many different ways – do not despair and think of turning challenges into opportunities. Good luck to everyone!

3 REFLECTIONS AND WAY AHEAD

The SEFI 2020 Doctoral Symposium was successfully converted to an interactive online format. 21 doctoral students and 17 seniors worked together in forming the future of the engineering education research community. It will be an interesting dilemma whether to go back to the physical format, if and when it is possible again, or continue to develop the remote format. The most difficult alternative would be to arrange a hybrid format, with participants both remotely and physically present. The experiences from 2020 certainly showed that a remote format was feasible, but there are some trade-offs. One great advantage was that participants came from an impressive range from different countries, both seniors and doctoral students. Many of them would not have been able to travel to the conference. On the other hand, some participants found that a full day online was quite wearying, perhaps most so for those located outside Eurocentric time zones. For those who are travelling anyway, a day of face-to-face meeting is less tiring and may be even more rewarding. However, if the DS is not tied to the physical presence at the SEFI conference, other completely different formats are possible and could be discussed. Finally, some advice was collected from participants in the SEFI Doctoral Symposium 2020 to a hypothetical person asking if they should attend next year:

- The field of Engineering Education is populated with researchers and practitioners with many different backgrounds. Each of them can teach you something useful, especially when you are not in the same field.
- I would encourage everyone to join the symposium and learn new things.
- Do it. Be very clear on what you want to gain from it.
- Attending the symposium will always have value even if it is only as a networking opportunity to meet new people and to share your own work. Beyond that you can take advantage of discussions with other students and more experienced researchers and perhaps pick up ideas and get feedback and support for your research work. It is always a winning formula :-)
- Definitely participate! You get to know so many people from your field, talking about your research feels very natural in the symposium and it is always good to talk to people outside your research group.
- Don't hesitate. It's a great opportunity to talk (passionately) about your PhD research with critical friends.
- Do it and prepare your main questions in advance
- If you have some things you are struggling with - which you probably do - and you want a new perspective on it, you should definitely join the symposium!

4 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank every single participant in the Doctoral Symposium over the years, doctoral students as well as seniors, because the success of the activity is a direct result of your engagement and enthusiasm. We thank the organisers of the SEFI Annual Conferences for great hospitality during the pre-conference day. We thank SEFI for being entrusted with the stimulating task of organising this activity. Finally, we gratefully acknowledge how SEFI supports the EER field in many ways, among them the Doctoral Symposium.

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